

Logical syllogisms with “Almost all, Most, Many, A few” and “Several”

Petra Murinová*, Vilém Novák

University of Ostrava, Institute for Research and Applications of Fuzzy Modeling, 30. dubna 22, 701 03 Ostrava 1, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Fuzzy natural logic
Intermediate quantifiers
Intermediate syllogisms
Quantifiers “A few” and “Several”

ABSTRACT

This paper delves into logical syllogisms featuring intermediate quantifiers. In our previous works, we established the validity of logical syllogisms involving fundamental intermediate quantifiers “Almost all”, “Most”, and “Many”. In this paper, we focus on syllogisms incorporating also the quantifiers “Several” and “A few (A little)”.

1. Introduction

In this article, we continue the study of generalized logical syllogisms with intermediate quantifiers. Note that quantifiers in natural language are expressions using which we quantify the number of some objects. In our papers [1–5] we developed a formal theory of intermediate quantifiers and focused on those whose definition is based on characterization of large part of the universe of quantification. Typical representatives are *all*, *almost all*, *most* and *many*.

There are, however, intermediate quantifiers whose meaning is opposite to the above ones and refers to a small part of the universe. Typical examples are *several*, *a few*, and *a little*. The first two quantifiers can be joined with a countable noun, while the latter with an uncountable one. Note that there is a difference between *a few* and *few* (*a little* and *little*) in a broader context where the former is a simple quantifier characterizing a certain number or amount corresponding to some, while the latter also carries a negative evaluation expressing non-satisfaction with a given amount. We will consider only the first cases because we do not have (so far) formal means to represent such an assessment.

According to Cambridge and Merriam-Webster dictionary definitions, “a few” or “several” typically denotes more than 1 or 2 but less than *many*. It is important to note that these quantifiers characterize specific sizes of (fuzzy) sets in our theory, where size is modeled using the concept of measure. The distinction between a “*a few*” and “*a little*” is absent, as both encompass a range and may involve a universe that is countable or uncountable.

Longman Thesaurus suggests that “*several*” generally implies a larger quantity than “*a few*”. The interpretation of “*a few*” could encompass two or three, while “*several*” might imply three or four. However, this interpretation heavily relies on the number of elements in the universe being considered, i.e., on the context. For instance, “a few books are detective stories” on a bookshelf with 20 books is a different number than “a few spectators already came to see the match” when the expected number is 2000. Thus, “*several*” conveys a greater quantity than “*a few*” but still implies a modest amount.

In [6], Zadeh already addressed non-trivial syllogisms with the quantifier “most” in both premises. He called them *Multiplicative Chaining Syllogisms*. We studied them from the point of view of natural fuzzy logic in [7].

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: Petra.Murinova@osu.cz (P. Murinová), Vilem.Novak@osu.cz (V. Novák).

In the sequel, we will call a logical syllogism with intermediate quantifiers an *intermediate syllogism*. It is called *classical* if it contains classical quantifiers \forall, \exists only. If it includes non-classical (intermediate) quantifiers in *both premises*, we will call it *non-trivial*. The latter may occur in the *third figure* only, while the validity of syllogism in the other figures requires at least one universal quantifier.

Many authors addressed other selected forms of logical syllogisms. Generalized syllogisms with interval quantifiers were developed in [8,9]. In connection with this, also extended syllogistic reasoning with the new quantifiers was proposed, see, for example, [6, 10–13]. There are also papers devoted to further generalization, assuming more premises. For example, Pereira-Fariña et al. [11] analyzed logical syllogisms with more premises based on the transformation of syllogistic reasoning into an optimization problem. Such syllogisms from point of view of fuzzy natural logic were introduced and formally analyzed in [14,15].

The main goals This paper follows up on our previous approach ([16,17]), where we introduced mathematical definitions of intermediate quantifiers “Several” and “A few”. Furthermore, we proved the monotonicity property concerning the other intermediate quantifiers. In the second publication, we continued the study of logical syllogisms related to new forms of intermediate quantifiers. We elaborated very briefly the first figure of syllogisms.

We will also focus on further elaboration of intermediate syllogisms with quantifiers “All, Almost all, Most, Many, Several, A few, Some”. Most interesting are *non-trivial syllogisms*, to which we devote a particular section since verifying their validity or invalidity is not as straightforward as in other figures.

This paper aims to extend the theory of intermediate quantifiers, specifically the new quantifiers “several” and “a few (a little)”. Subsequently, new forms of logical syllogisms in all figures are syntactically proven. Notably, the third figure is particularly interesting as it makes it possible to consider non-trivial syllogisms.

Structure of this paper The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 contains basic facts about fuzzy type theory and the theory of evaluative linguistic expressions. In Section 3, we introduce the formal theory of intermediate quantifiers. In Section 4, we introduce new quantifiers *a few* and *several* and formalize the concept of logical syllogism. Section 5 is devoted to intermediate syllogism of Figures I, II, IV and Section 6 to syllogisms of Figure III. The last Section 7 contains conclusion remarks.

2. Preliminaries

2.1. Fuzzy type theory

The theory of intermediate quantifiers has been formulated using the tools of higher-order fuzzy logic (fuzzy type theory; \mathbb{L} -FTT). The algebra of truth values is an MV_{Δ} -algebra $\mathcal{E} = \langle E, \vee, \wedge, \otimes, \rightarrow, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1}, \Delta \rangle$ where $\mathbf{0}$ is the least and $\mathbf{1}$ is the greatest element, respectively. We will usually consider the Łukasiewicz one with the support $E = [0, 1]$.

The fundamental syntactical entities in \mathbb{L} -FTT are classical and revolve around the concepts of *type* and *formula* (refer to [18]). Atomic types include ϵ (elements) and o (truth values). More general types are defined as follows: if α and β are types, then $(\beta\alpha)$ is a type. We represent types using Greek letters, and the collective set of all types is denoted as *Types*.

The *language* J of \mathbb{L} -FTT encompasses variables x_{α}, \dots , special constants c_{α}, \dots (where $\alpha \in \text{Types}$), the symbol λ , and brackets. Notably, we will consider special constants $E(o\alpha)\alpha$ (fuzzy equality) for each $\alpha \in \text{Types}$, $C(o\alpha)\alpha$ (conjunction), $D(o\alpha)\alpha$ (delta operation on truth values), and the description operator $I_{\epsilon(o\epsilon)}$.

Formulas are constructed from variables, constants (each with a specific type), and the symbol λ . Consequently, each formula A is attributed a type, denoted as A_{α} . A set of formulas of type α is denoted by $Form_{\alpha}$. The set of all formulas is denoted by $Form = \bigcup_{\alpha \in \text{Types}} Form_{\alpha}$. If we write $A \in Form_{\alpha}$ then it is the same as writing just A_{α} . We will often use this possibility to simplify the notation.

Each formula is assigned a type which in semantics represents functions over sets of specific kind. To make the formulas more readable, we often write the type in the beginning of a formula only and then omit it, assuming that it is clear from the context of use.

Formulas in \mathbb{L} -FTT are interpreted as follows. A model is

$$\mathcal{M} = \langle (M_{\alpha}, \stackrel{\circ}{=}_{\alpha})_{\alpha \in \text{Types}}, \mathcal{E} \rangle$$

where M_{α} are sets of elements of type α , $\stackrel{\circ}{=}_{\alpha}$ is a fuzzy equality and \mathcal{E} is an algebra of truth values.

If \mathcal{M} is a model, then $\mathcal{M}(A_o) \in M_o = E$ represents a truth value, $\mathcal{M}(A_{\epsilon}) \in M_{\epsilon}$ represents some element, and $\mathcal{M}(A_{\beta\alpha}) : M_{\alpha} \rightarrow M_{\beta}$ is a function.

In the sequel we will use special (derived) formulas Y_{oo} and \hat{Y}_{oo} , using which we can express that the given formula A_o has in every model a non-zero or general (i.e., belonging to $(0, 1)$) truth value, respectively.

$$Y_{oo} \equiv \lambda z_o \cdot \neg \Delta(\neg z_o), \tag{non-zero truth value}$$

$$\hat{Y}_{oo} \equiv \lambda z_o \cdot \neg \Delta(z_o \vee \neg z_o). \tag{general truth value}$$

Both formulas Y_{oo} as well as \hat{Y}_{oo} are crisp.

We use the following theorem in the subsequent proofs of logical syllogism validity.

Theorem 2.1 ([19,20]). Let T be a consistent theory, $A \in \text{Form}_{o\alpha}$ and $\mathbf{u}_{1,\alpha}, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{n,\alpha}$, $\alpha \in \text{Types}$ be new special constants that do not belong to the language $J(T)$. If $T \vdash (\exists x_{1,\alpha}) \dots (\exists x_{n,\alpha}) \Delta A$ then $T \cup \{A_{x_{\alpha,1}, \dots, x_{\alpha,n}}[\mathbf{u}_{\alpha,1}, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{\alpha,n}]\}$ is a conservative extension of T .

In the sequel, we will often use the formula expressing sharp ordering of truth values:

$$x_o <_{(oo)o} y_o \equiv (x_o \Rightarrow y_o) \& \neg \Delta(x_o \equiv y_o).$$

2.2. The theory of evaluative linguistic expressions

The theory of intermediate quantifiers is built upon the foundation of evaluative linguistic expressions, which are expressions of natural language, such as *short*, *medium*, *bitter*, *very strong*, *rich*, *extremely deep*, etc. A detailed formal theory of them is presented in [20]. With a less formal account including formulas for direct computation it is available also in [21].

The semantics of evaluative linguistic expressions is modeled in a special formal theory T^{Ev} of L-FTT. The language J^{Ev} comprises, among others, special constants for truth (\top), falsity (\perp), and the middle truth value (\dagger) and an additional fuzzy equality on the set of truth values. This is represented by the constant $\sim \in \text{Form}_{(oo)o}$. A special role has linguistic hedges that are represented by special constants $\{Ex, Si, Ve, ML, Ro, QR, VR\}$, that represent the linguistic hedges (*extremely*, *significantly*, *very*, *more or less*, *roughly*, *quite roughly*, *very roughly*, respectively). A set of additional constants $(\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}, \dots) \in \text{Form}_o$ where each hedge \mathbf{v} is uniquely associated with one triple of these constants.

Special formulas $Sm \in \text{Form}_{oo(oo)}$ (*small*), $Me \in \text{Form}_{oo(oo)}$ (*medium*), $Bi \in \text{Form}_{oo(oo)}$ (*big*), and $Ze \in \text{Form}_{oo(oo)}$ (*zero*) represent evaluative expressions that can be modified by linguistic hedges.

The evaluative linguistic expressions are represented in T^{Ev} by formulas of the form

$$Sm \mathbf{v}, Me \mathbf{v}, Bi \mathbf{v}, Ze \mathbf{v} \in \text{Form}_{oo} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{v} is a hedge. For instance, $SmVe$ represents the evaluative expression “*very small*”. We also introduce an *empty hedge* $\bar{\mathbf{v}}$. For example, $Bi\bar{\mathbf{v}}$ represents the expression “*big*”. The connective Δ_{oo} is considered as a linguistic hedge “*utmost*”. Each hedge is characterized by three parameters $\mathbf{a}, \mathbf{b}, \mathbf{c}$ (for the details, see the references).

The model of the semantics relies on an *additional separated fuzzy equality* \sim using which we define special formulas for *left horizon* $LH \equiv \lambda z_o \cdot \perp \sim z_o$, *middle horizon* $MH \equiv \lambda z_o \cdot \dagger \sim z_o$ and *right horizon* $RH \equiv \lambda z_o \cdot \top \sim z_o$. These, in combination with linguistic hedges define semantics of the above considered evaluative expressions.

If we do not need to consider specific evaluative expression then we will use the metavariable Ev which replaces arbitrary formula for an evaluative expression from (1).

It has been demonstrated that evaluative expressions imprecisely determine position on a bounded linearly ordered scale. Based on that, we define a *context*, represented by a triple of elements $v_L, v_S, v_R \in M_\alpha$ for some type α such that $v_L < v_S < v_R$.¹ Then $x \in w$ iff $x \in [v_L, v_S] \cup [v_S, v_R] \subset M_\alpha$. By the *standard context* we mean $\langle 0, 0.5, 1 \rangle$.

Furthermore, we define the concepts of intension and extension. To simplify explanation, we omit context from the theory of intermediate quantifiers. However, incorporating it into formulas is straightforward. Further details on the theory of evaluative linguistic expressions can be found in the references.

We can introduce a relation of partial ordering of hedges as follows:

$$\ll_{(oo)(oo)} \equiv \lambda p_{oo} \lambda q_{oo} \cdot (\forall z_o) \Delta(pz \Rightarrow qz). \quad (2)$$

Theorem 2.2.

(a)

$$T^{\text{Ev}} \vdash \Delta \ll Ex \ll Si \ll Ve \ll \bar{\mathbf{v}} \ll ML \ll Ro \ll QR \ll VR. \quad (3)$$

(b) Let $\mathbf{v}_1 \ll \mathbf{v}_2$ and $Ev_{\mathbf{v}_1}, Ev_{\mathbf{v}_2}$ be evaluative expressions differing only in the hedges $\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2$, respectively. Then

$$T^{\text{Ev}} \vdash (\forall z)(Ev_{\mathbf{v}_1} z \Rightarrow (Ev_{\mathbf{v}_2} z)). \quad (4)$$

Proof. (a) was proved in [16, Lemma 1].

(b) was proved in [20, Theorem 9(a)]. \square

Theorem 2.3.

$$T^{\text{Ev}} \vdash (\forall z)((Bi \mathbf{v})z \Rightarrow \neg (Sm \mathbf{v})z) \quad (5)$$

¹ The context is a formula w_α interpreted by a function $w : E \rightarrow M_\alpha$, by means of which an ordering on M_α is induced and, consequently, these three elements are determined.

Fig. 1. Extensions of evaluative expressions $Sm\bar{v}$, $\neg Sm\bar{v}$ and $BiEx$ in the context $[0, 0.4] \cup [0.4, 1]$ with marked interpretation of points $a_{\neg Sm\bar{v}}$, a_{BiEx} and $\neg c_{Sm\bar{v}}$.

Proof. See [20, Theorem 8(c)]. \square

Recall that extensions of evaluative linguistic expressions are determined by three constants $(\mathbf{a}_v, \mathbf{b}_v, \mathbf{c}_v)$ assigned to each linguistic hedge v . Then, we can define special formulas $a_{Smv} \equiv I_{o(o\alpha)} \cdot \lambda x_o \Delta(LH x \equiv \mathbf{a}_v)$, $c_{Smv} \equiv I_{o(o\alpha)} \cdot \lambda x_o \Delta(LH x \equiv \mathbf{c}_v)$, $a_{Bi\bar{v}} \equiv I_{o(o\alpha)} \cdot \lambda x_o \Delta(RH x \equiv \mathbf{a}_v)$, $c_{Bi\bar{v}} \equiv I_{o(o\alpha)} \cdot \lambda x_o \Delta(RH x \equiv \mathbf{c}_v)$ (cf. [19]). Specific cases of these values are depicted in Fig. 1. Note that $T^{Ev} \vdash a_{\neg Sm\bar{v}} \equiv c_{Sm\bar{v}}$.

A special evaluative expression is Zero. A mathematical model of its meaning in the standard context is

$$Ze_{oo} \equiv \lambda z_o (Smv_{Ze})z_o, \tag{6}$$

and $Ze_{(o\alpha)(\alpha o)} \equiv \lambda w_{\alpha o} \lambda x_{\alpha} (Smv_{Ze})wx$ if a general context w is considered. The special hedge v_{Ze} has in the ordering \ll the position

$$T^{Ev} \vdash \Delta \ll v_{Ze} \ll Ex.$$

Hence,

$$T^{Ev} \vdash Ze w_{\alpha o} \subseteq (SmEx)w_{\alpha o}$$

due to Theorem 2.2. To define mathematical model of zero, we put $c_{v_{Ze}} = \perp$ and obtain

$$c_{Ze} \equiv I \lambda x_o \cdot \Delta(LH x \equiv \mathbf{c}_{v_{Ze}}) \tag{7}$$

which gives $c_{Ze} = \perp$.

Do not confuse $\mathbf{c}_{v_{Ze}}$ and c_{Ze} . While the former is a parameter of the linguistic hedge v_{Ze} for Zero, the latter is the corresponding threshold on the universe, which, in this case, is the set of truth values. If we consider a context $w = \langle 0, v_S, v_R \rangle$ then c_{Ze} would equal 0 in the context $[0, v_S] \cup [v_S, v_R]$.

Below, we introduce the evaluative expression “positively (hedge)small” that is formally defined by

$$+ Smv \equiv \lambda t_o \cdot (Smv)t_o \& \neg(Ze v_{Ze})t_o. \tag{8}$$

Clearly, $+ Smv \in Form_{oo}$.

3. Theory of intermediate quantifiers

Recall that the meaning of intermediate quantifiers lies between the meanings of the classical ones \forall and \exists . Unlike the latter, which are symbols interpreted by operations on the set of truth values, intermediate quantifiers are represented by formulas of a special theory T^{Ev} of L-FTT. The quantification proceeds over a universe represented by a fuzzy set whose size is determined by a measure. For detailed and necessary formal definitions, please see the references.

In the rest of this paper we will often consider a certain type $\alpha \in Types$. Whenever work with a set M of some model then we always assume that it is a set of given type α , unless specified otherwise.

Definition 3.1. Let $\mathcal{S} \subseteq Types$ be a selected set of types and $P = \{R \in Form_{o(o\alpha)(\alpha o)} \mid \alpha \in \mathcal{S}\}$ be a set of new constants. Let T be a consistent extension of the theory T^{Ev} in the language $J(T) \supseteq J^{Ev} \cup P$. We say that the theory T contains *intermediate quantifiers* w.r.t. the set of types \mathcal{S} if for all $\alpha \in \mathcal{S}$ the following is provable:

- (i) $T \vdash (\exists z_{o\alpha}) \mathbf{M}_{o(o\alpha)} z_{o\alpha}$,
- (ii) $T \vdash (\forall z_{o\alpha}) (\exists x_{o\alpha}) (\mathbf{M}_{o(o\alpha)} z_{o\alpha} \Rightarrow (\Delta(x_{o\alpha} \subseteq z_{o\alpha}) \& \hat{Y}((\mu z_{o\alpha})x_{o\alpha})))$.

In the sequel, we will denote the theory due to Definition 3.1 by T^{IQ} and fix a selected set of types \mathcal{S} .

Definition 3.2. Let $R \in \text{Form}_{o(\alpha)(\alpha)}$ be a formula where $\alpha \in \text{Types}$ is an arbitrary type.

(i) A formula $\mu \in \text{Form}_{o(\alpha)(\alpha)}$ defined by

$$\mu_{o(\alpha)(\alpha)} \equiv \lambda z_{\alpha} \lambda x_{\alpha} (Rz_{\alpha})x_{\alpha} \quad (9)$$

represents a *measure on fuzzy sets* in the universe of type $\alpha \in \text{Types}$ if it has the following properties:

$$(M1) \ \Delta(x_{\alpha} \subseteq z_{\alpha}) \ \& \ \Delta(y_{\alpha} \subseteq z_{\alpha}) \ \& \ \Delta(x_{\alpha} \subseteq y_{\alpha}) \Rightarrow ((\mu z_{\alpha})x_{\alpha} \Rightarrow (\mu z_{\alpha})y_{\alpha}),$$

$$(M2) \ \Delta(x_{\alpha} \subseteq z_{\alpha}) \Rightarrow ((\mu z_{\alpha})(z_{\alpha} \setminus x_{\alpha}) \equiv \neg(\mu z_{\alpha})x_{\alpha}),$$

$$(M3) \ \Delta(x_{\alpha} \subseteq y_{\alpha}) \ \& \ \Delta(x_{\alpha} \subseteq z_{\alpha}) \ \& \ \Delta(y_{\alpha} \subseteq z_{\alpha}) \Rightarrow ((\mu z_{\alpha})x_{\alpha} \Rightarrow (\mu y_{\alpha})x_{\alpha})$$

where $x_{\alpha}, y_{\alpha}, z_{\alpha}$ are variables representing fuzzy sets.

(ii) The following formula characterizes *measurable fuzzy sets* of a given type α :

$$\mathbf{M}_{o(\alpha)} \equiv \lambda z_{\alpha} \cdot \neg \Delta(z_{\alpha} \equiv \emptyset_{\alpha}) \ \& \ \Delta(\mu z_{\alpha})z_{\alpha} \ \& \ (\forall x_{\alpha})(\forall y_{\alpha}) \Delta((M1) \ \& \ (M3)) \ \& \ (\forall x_{\alpha}) \Delta(M2) \quad (10)$$

where (M1)–(M3) are the axioms from (i).

Lemma 3.3. [19] Let T be a theory whose language contains a constant $R_{o(\alpha)(\alpha)}$ for some $\alpha \in \text{Types}$. Let $A, B \in \text{Form}_{\alpha}$ and $T \vdash \mathbf{M}_{o(\alpha)} B$. Then

$$(a) \ T \vdash \neg(\mu B)\emptyset.$$

$$(b) \ \text{If } T \vdash B \subseteq A \text{ then } T \vdash (\mu B)A \equiv \top.$$

We can observe that the measure μ is normalized, i.e., in every model, it achieves values between 0 and 1. By (b), $T \vdash (\mu B)B \equiv \top$. It follows from Definition 3.2 that the empty (fuzzy) set has a zero measure.

Lemma 3.4. Let $B \in \text{Form}_{\alpha}$ be a formula such that $\vdash \mathbf{M}(B_{\alpha})$. Then for any $u \in \text{Form}_{\alpha}$

$$\vdash (\forall u_{\alpha})(\Delta(u_{\alpha} \equiv \emptyset_{\alpha}) \Rightarrow ((\mu B_{\alpha})u_{\alpha} \equiv \perp)).$$

Proof. $\vdash (\mu B_{\alpha})\emptyset_{\alpha} \equiv \perp$ by Lemma 3.3. Then the lemma follows from the deduction theorem by adding $u_{\alpha} \equiv \emptyset_{\alpha}$ as the assumption and using generalization. \square

Lemma 3.5. Let $B \in \text{Form}_{\alpha}$ be a formula such that $\vdash \mathbf{M}(B_{\alpha})$. Then for any $u \in \text{Form}_{\alpha}$ and $x \in \text{Form}_{\alpha}$

$$T^{\text{Ev}} \vdash \Upsilon \neg(Ze \nu)((\mu B_{\alpha})u_{\alpha}) \Rightarrow \Upsilon(\exists x_{\alpha})(u_{\alpha}x).$$

Proof. (L.1) $\vdash \neg((\mu B_{\alpha})u_{\alpha} \equiv \perp) \Rightarrow \neg \Delta(u_{\alpha} \equiv \emptyset_{\alpha})$ (Lemma 3.4, substitution and contraposition)

$$(L.2) \ T^{\text{Ev}} \vdash \Upsilon(\neg Ze \nu)(\mu B_{\alpha})u_{\alpha} \Rightarrow (c_{Ze} < (\mu B_{\alpha})u_{\alpha}) \text{ (proof of [19, Lemma 5(g)])}$$

$$(L.3) \ T^{\text{Ev}} \vdash c_{Ze} \equiv \perp \text{ (by the formula (7) which gives } c_{Ze} = \perp)$$

$$(L.4) \ T^{\text{Ev}} \vdash \Upsilon(\neg Ze \nu)(\mu B_{\alpha})u_{\alpha} \Rightarrow \neg \Delta((\mu B_{\alpha})u_{\alpha} \equiv \perp) \text{ (L.2, L.3, definition of “<”, properties of } \mathbb{L}\text{-FTT)}$$

$$(L.5) \ T^{\text{Ev}} \vdash \Upsilon(\neg Ze \nu)(\mu B_{\alpha})u_{\alpha} \Rightarrow \neg \Delta(u_{\alpha} \equiv \emptyset_{\alpha}) \text{ (L.1, L.4, properties of } \mathbb{L}\text{-FTT)}$$

$$(L.6) \ T^{\text{Ev}} \vdash \Upsilon(\neg Ze \nu)(\mu B_{\alpha})u_{\alpha} \Rightarrow \neg \Delta(\forall x) \neg(u_{\alpha}x) \text{ (L.5, def. of } \emptyset, \text{ properties of } \mathbb{L}\text{-FTT)}$$

$$(L.7) \ T^{\text{Ev}} \vdash \Upsilon(\neg Ze \nu)(\mu B_{\alpha})u_{\alpha} \Rightarrow \neg \Delta \neg(\exists x)u_{\alpha}x \text{ (L.6, properties of } \mathbb{L}\text{-FTT)}$$

$$(L.8) \ T^{\text{Ev}} \vdash \Upsilon(\neg Ze \nu)(\mu B_{\alpha})u_{\alpha} \Rightarrow \Upsilon(\exists x)u_{\alpha}x \text{ (L.7, def. of } \Upsilon, \text{ properties of } \mathbb{L}\text{-FTT)} \quad \square$$

From this lemma it follows that if the measure of a fuzzy set u_{α} is non-zero then there exists an element x_{α} in u_{α} with non-zero membership degree.

For the definition of intermediate quantifiers, we need a special operation *cut of a fuzzy set* $y \in \text{Form}_{\alpha}$ by a fuzzy set $z \in \text{Form}_{\alpha}$:

$$y|z \equiv \lambda x_{\alpha} \cdot zx \ \& \ \Delta(\Upsilon(zx) \Rightarrow (yx \equiv zx)). \quad (11)$$

This operation is motivated as follows. Let fuzzy sets $B, Z \subseteq M$ be given, then the operation $B|Z$ cuts B by taking only those $m \in M$ whose membership $B(m)$ is equal to $Z(m)$, otherwise $(B|Z)(m) = 0$. If there is no m with this property then $B|Z = \emptyset$. Informally, this means that we “pick” out selected elements from B together with their membership degrees and omit the rest.

Lemma 3.6. Let $B, Y, Z \subseteq M$. Then

$$(a) \ [B|Z \subseteq B] = 1 \text{ and } B|Z = Z|B,^2$$

² The symbol $[\cdot]$ denotes truth value of the expression inside.

(b) If $[B|Y \subseteq B|Z] > 0$ then $[B|Y \subseteq B|Z] = 1$.

Proof. (a) was proved in [22].

(b) By definition, $[B|Y \subseteq B|Z] = \bigwedge_{m \in \mathcal{M}} ((B|Y)(m) \rightarrow (B|Z)(m))$. However, either $(B|Y)(m) = 0$ or $(B|Y)(m) = (B|Z)(m)$. In both cases $((B|Y)(m) \rightarrow (B|Z)(m)) = 1$. \square

Lemma 3.7. Let $B \in Form_{o\alpha}$ be a formula for some $\alpha \in Types$. Then

- (a) $T^{IQ} \vdash (Bi\Delta)((\mu B)(B|B)) \equiv \top$,
 (b) $T^{IQ} \vdash (Sm\Delta)((\mu B)(B|B)) \equiv \perp$.

Proof. This follows from [19, Lemma 8] and [20, Theorem 7]. \square

Definition 3.8. Let us denote by $Ev \in Form_{o\alpha}$ a metavariable denoting a formula that represents some evaluative linguistic expression. Let $z \in Form_{o\alpha}$, $x \in Form_{\alpha}$ be variables and $A, B \in Form_{o\alpha}$ be formulas such that $T^{IQ} \vdash M_{o(\alpha\alpha)} B$, $\alpha \in \mathcal{S}$.

(i) An intermediate quantifier of type $\langle 1, 1 \rangle$ is one of the following formulas:

$$(Q_{Ev}^{\forall} x)(B, A) \equiv (\exists z)[(\forall x)((B|z)x \Rightarrow Ax) \wedge Ev((\mu B)(B|z))], \quad (12)$$

$$(Q_{Ev}^{\exists} x)(B, A) \equiv (\exists z)[(\exists x)((B|z)x \wedge Ax) \wedge Ev((\mu B)(B|z))]. \quad (13)$$

(ii) An intermediate quantifier of type $\langle 1, 1 \rangle$ with the presupposition (existential import) is one of the following formulas:

$$(*Q_{Ev}^{\forall} x)(B, A) \equiv (\exists z)[((\exists x)(B|z)x \& (\forall x)((B|z)x \Rightarrow Ax)) \wedge Ev((\mu B)(B|z))], \quad (14)$$

$$(*Q_{Ev}^{\exists} x)(B, A) \equiv (\exists z)[(\neg(\exists x)(B|z)x \vee ((\exists x)((B|z)x \wedge Ax) \wedge Ev((\mu B)(B|z)))]. \quad (15)$$

Formula $B \in Form_{o\alpha}$ represents a *universe of quantification*.

Either of the quantifiers (12)–(15) construes the sentence

$\langle \text{Quantifier} \rangle B$'s are A .

By replacing the metavariable Ev in (12)–(15) with a formula representing a specific evaluative linguistic expression, we will get the definition of the concrete intermediate quantifier. Several intermediate quantifiers springing from the interpretation of Peterson's approach in [23]) are defined as follows: If we substitute concrete evaluative linguistic expressions in place of Ev , we obtain the following intermediate quantifiers:

$$\mathbf{A:} \text{ All } B\text{'s are } A := (Q_{Bi\Delta}^{\forall} x)(B, A) \equiv (\forall x)(Bx \Rightarrow Ax),$$

$$\mathbf{E:} \text{ No } B\text{'s are } A := (Q_{Bi\Delta}^{\forall} x)(B, \neg A) \equiv (\forall x)(Bx \Rightarrow \neg Ax),$$

$$\mathbf{P:} \text{ Almost all } B\text{'s are } A := (Q_{BiEx}^{\forall} x)(B, A)$$

$$\mathbf{B:} \text{ Almost all } B\text{'s are not } A := (Q_{BiEx}^{\forall} x)(B, \neg A)$$

$$\mathbf{T:} \text{ Most } B\text{'s are } A := (Q_{BiVe}^{\forall} x)(B, A)$$

$$\mathbf{D:} \text{ Most } B\text{'s are not } A := (Q_{BiVe}^{\forall} x)(B, \neg A)$$

$$\mathbf{K:} \text{ Many } B\text{'s are } A := (Q_{-Sm}^{\forall} x)(B, A)$$

$$\mathbf{G:} \text{ Many } B\text{'s are not } A := (Q_{-Sm}^{\forall} x)(B, \neg A)$$

$$\mathbf{I:} \text{ Some } B\text{'s are } A := (Q_{Bi\Delta}^{\exists} x)(B, A) \equiv (\exists x)(Bx \wedge Ax),$$

$$\mathbf{O:} \text{ Some } B\text{'s are not } A := (Q_{Bi\Delta}^{\exists} x)(B, \neg A) \equiv (\exists x)(Bx \wedge \neg Ax).$$

In what follows, we will often refer to a specific intermediate quantifier by the appropriate bold letter introduced above.

Remark 3.9 (Notation). Careful notation in any logical theory requires to distinguish between formulas and their interpretation in a model. We will usually use the same letter but add the type, if it is a formula. For example $A_{o\alpha}$ is a formula whose interpretation in

a model \mathcal{M} is a fuzzy set $A \subseteq M_\alpha$ where M_α is a set of all elements of type α in \mathcal{M} . We use special notation for the interpretation of the formula $Ev(\mu(B)(B|z))$, namely, if \mathcal{M} is a model and $B_{o\alpha}, z_{o\alpha}$ are formulas then we put $Z = \mathcal{M}_p(z)$ and

$$F_{Ev}^R(B, B|Z) = \mathcal{M}_p(Ev(\mu(B)(B|z))).$$

The following theorem was proved in [4] on the basis of the original definition of the intermediate quantifiers. For clarity, we will present this proof with the modified definition.

Theorem 3.10 ([4]). *Let $A_{o\alpha}, B_{o\alpha}$ be formulas. Then the following is provable in the theory T^{IQ} for the above defined quantifiers:*

$$T^{IQ} \vdash (A) \Rightarrow (P), T^{IQ} \vdash (P) \Rightarrow (T), T^{IQ} \vdash (T) \Rightarrow (K),$$

$$T^{IQ} \vdash (E) \Rightarrow (B), T^{IQ} \vdash (B) \Rightarrow (D), T^{IQ} \vdash (D) \Rightarrow (G).$$

Proof. By [4, Theorem 1(g)], if $T^{IQ} \vdash \mathbf{v}_1 \ll \mathbf{v}_2$ then $T^{IQ} \vdash (Bi \mathbf{v}_1)((\mu B)z) \Rightarrow (Bi \mathbf{v}_2)((\mu B)z)$. From it follows that

$$T^{IQ} \vdash (Bi \mathbf{v}_1)((\mu B)B|z) \wedge (\forall x)(zx \Rightarrow Ax) \Rightarrow (Bi \mathbf{v}_2)((\mu B)B|z) \wedge (\forall x)(zx \Rightarrow Ax).$$

Then we apply generalization and the properties of quantifiers. The theorem follows after assigning specific hedges for $\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2$. \square

In [19], we explained motivation for introducing the following definition.

Definition 3.11. Let T^{IQ} be a theory containing intermediate quantifiers w.r.t. a set of types \mathcal{S} . Let $B \in Form_{o\alpha}$ for some $\alpha \in \mathcal{S}$ be a selected formula. We say that B is *regular* in some consistent extension T of T^{IQ} if the following is provable:

$$(TB1) T \vdash (\exists x_\alpha) \Delta Bx,$$

$$(TB2) T \vdash (\exists v_{o\alpha}) [(\forall x_\alpha)(Y(B|v)x \Rightarrow Y((B|v)x)^2) \& ((\mu B)(B|v) > \dagger)].$$

By (TB1), the regular fuzzy set B must be normal, and by (TB2), it must contain a fuzzy subset in which membership degrees of elements x are “sufficiently high”. The latter is assured by the first subformula of (TB2). Namely, in any model $\mathcal{M} \models T$, if the truth value $\mathcal{M}_p((B|v)x) > 0$, then it must be greater than 0.5. The second subformula assures that $v_{o\alpha}$ is sufficiently large w.r.t. the fuzzy set $B_{o\alpha}$.

Lemma 3.12. *Let \mathcal{M} be a model of T^{IQ} , p an assignment and $B_{o\alpha}$ a regular formula. Let $A, C \in Form_{o\alpha}$ be formulas such that $\mathcal{M}_p(A), \mathcal{M}_p(C) \subseteq \mathcal{M}_p(B)$.*

(a) *If $\mathcal{M}_p((\mu B)(B|A)) > a$ and $\mathcal{M}_p((\mu B)(B|C)) > b$ such that $a \otimes b > 0$ then³*

$$\mathcal{M}_p(B|A) \wp \mathcal{M}_p(B|C) \neq \emptyset.$$

(b) *If $\mathcal{M}_p((\mu B)(B|A)) > \mathcal{M}(\dagger)$ and $\mathcal{M}_p((\mu B)(B|C)) > \mathcal{M}(\dagger)$ then*

$$\mathcal{M}_p(B|A) \wp \mathcal{M}_p(B|C) \neq \emptyset.$$

(c) *If $\mathcal{M}_p((\mu B)(B|A)) > 0$ and $\mathcal{M}_p((\mu B)(B|C)) = 1$ then*

$$\mathcal{M}_p(B|A) \wp \mathcal{M}_p(B|C) \neq \emptyset.$$

(d) *If $\mathcal{M}_p((\mu B)(B|A)) > \mathcal{M}(\dagger)$ and $\mathcal{M}_p(Bi \mathbf{v}((\mu B)(B|C))) = 1$ for arbitrary hedge \mathbf{v} then*

$$\mathcal{M}_p(B|A) \wp \mathcal{M}_p(B|C) \neq \emptyset.$$

(e) *If $\mathcal{M}_p((\mu B)(B|A)) > 0$ and $\mathcal{M}_p(Bi \Delta((\mu B)(B|C))) = 1$ then*

$$\mathcal{M}_p(B|A) \wp \mathcal{M}_p(B|C) \neq \emptyset.$$

Proof. (a) Note that $a \otimes b > 0$ implies $a > \neg b$. Let us assume that $\mathcal{M}_p(B|A) \wp \mathcal{M}_p(B|C) = \emptyset$. Then for all $m \in M_\alpha$, $\mathcal{M}_p(B|A)(m) \otimes \mathcal{M}_p(B|C)(m) = 0$, i.e., $\mathcal{M}_p(B|A)(m) \leq \neg \mathcal{M}_p(B|C)(m)$ and we conclude that $\mathcal{M}_p(B|A) \subseteq \mathcal{M}_p(B \setminus (B|C))$. But then

$$\mathcal{M}_p((\mu B)(B|A)) \leq \neg \mathcal{M}_p((\mu B)(B|C)) = \neg b$$

which contradicts to $\mathcal{M}_p((\mu B)(B|A)) > a > \neg b$.

³ $\wp_{((o\alpha)(o\alpha)(o\alpha))} \equiv \lambda x_{o\alpha} \lambda y_{o\alpha} \lambda u_\alpha \cdot (x_{o\alpha} u_\alpha \& y_{o\alpha} u_\alpha)$.

(b), (c) follow directly from (a).

(d) follows from (a) and the definition of the meaning of $Bi\mathbf{v}$ (cf. [20] and elsewhere).

(e) Using Lemma 3.4 we can prove that $\mathcal{M}_p(B|A) \neq \emptyset$. From the semantics of $Bi\Delta$ and Lemma 3.7(a), we conclude that $\mathcal{M}_p(Bi\Delta((\mu B)(B|C))) = 1$ implies $\mathcal{M}_p(C) = \mathcal{M}_p(B)$. Then (d) follows from the assumption. \square

4. New quantifiers and generalized syllogisms with them

4.1. Definitions of “A few, Several, A little”

First we introduce a special evaluative expression *positive* $\langle hedge \rangle$ *small*

$${}^+Sm\mathbf{v} \equiv \lambda t_o \cdot (Sm\mathbf{v})t_o \ \& \ \neg(Ze\bar{\mathbf{v}})t_o. \quad (16)$$

Clearly, ${}^+Sm\mathbf{v} \in Form_{oo}$.

Definition 4.1. Let T^{IQ} be a theory containing intermediate quantifiers w.r.t. a set of types \mathcal{S} , $z \in Form_{oa}$, $x \in Form_a$ and $A, B \in Form_{oa}$ be the same as in Definition 3.8. The following are new quantifiers:

(F) “A few (A little) B ’s are A ” := $(Q_{+SmSi}^{\forall} x)(B, A)$.

(V) “A few (A little) B ’s are not A ” := $(Q_{+SmSi}^{\forall} x)(B, \neg A)$.

(S) “Several B ’s are A ” := $(Q_{+SmVe}^{\forall} x)(B, A)$.

(Z) “Several B ’s are not A ” := $(Q_{+SmVe}^{\forall} x)(B, \neg A)$.

Please be aware that in this definition, there is no formal distinction between “A few” and “A little”. The disparity lies solely in the applied measure and becomes apparent only when a particular model \mathcal{M} is taken into account. Specifically, if the support of the fuzzy set $\mathcal{M}(B_{oa})$ is countable based on the corresponding measure, then (F) or (V) interprets as “A few”. Conversely, if it is uncountable, then it interprets as “A little”.

Note that the use of *positive* $\langle hedge \rangle$ *small* in Definition 4.1 is necessary. Indeed, the empirical observation reveals that the empty fuzzy set must be excluded. For example:

“Several cows graze on the meadow”

cannot mean that there is no cow in the meadow.

4.2. Monotonicity property of new quantifiers

When considering fuzzy sets over a universe with a limited number of elements (e.g., 3 — 6) then it is possible to identify (fuzzy) sets with sufficiently large measure but simultaneously identifying (fuzzy) sets with significantly small measure becomes challenging. For instance, if we examine a set with 4 elements, a set with 2 elements may have a standard measure of 0.5, indicating it as “not small”, while a singleton has a measure of 0.25, which can hardly be deemed “significantly small”.

The following two properties assert that within a given fuzzy set $z|y$, there exists a notably small yet non-empty fuzzy set $z|s$, with the size of fuzzy sets measured using the measure μ :

$$NSQ_{o(oa)} \equiv \lambda z_{oa} \cdot (\forall y_{oa})(\exists s_{oa})\Delta[\neg Sm\bar{\mathbf{v}}((\mu z)(z|y)) \Rightarrow (z|s) \subseteq (z|y) \ \& \ {}^+SmSi((\mu z)(z|s))], \quad (17)$$

$$PSQ_{o(oa)} \equiv \lambda z_{oa} \cdot (\forall y_{oa})(\exists s_{oa})\Delta[Sm\bar{\mathbf{v}}((\mu z)(z|y)) \Rightarrow (z|s) \subseteq (z|y) \ \& \ {}^+SmSi((\mu z)(z|s))]. \quad (18)$$

The property **NSQ** assures existence of a significantly small fuzzy subset inside a non-small fuzzy set and **PSQ** assures the same for small fuzzy sets. While such properties are intuitively reasonable, they do not imply from the axioms of measure. Therefore, we cannot adopt (17) or (18) as an axiom universally valid for all fuzzy sets z_{oa} .

In the rest of this paper, by T we denote some consistent extension of the theory T^{IQ} in which axiom (17) or (18) holds for any universe of quantification. Eventually, we will also assume that T contains regular fuzzy sets in the sense of Definition 3.11.

Lemma 4.2.

(a) Let $T \vdash NSQ B_{oa}$ and $\mathbf{v} \in \{Ex, Si, Ve, \bar{\mathbf{v}}\}$. Then

$$T \vdash (\forall y_{oa})(\exists s_{oa})\Delta[Bi\mathbf{v}((\mu B)(B|y)) \Rightarrow (B|s) \subseteq (B|y) \ \& \ {}^+SmSi((\mu B)(B|s))] \quad (19)$$

(b) Let $T \vdash PSQ B_{oa}$ and $\mathbf{v} \in \{Ve, \bar{\mathbf{v}}\}$. Then

$$T \vdash (\forall y_{oa})(\exists s_{oa})\Delta[Sm\mathbf{v}((\mu B)(B|y)) \Rightarrow (B|s) \subseteq (B|y) \ \& \ {}^+SmSi((\mu B)(B|s))] \quad (20)$$

Proof. (a) Using substitution in axiom (17) we can extend conservatively the theory T by a new constant $\mathbf{u}_{o\alpha}$ and obtain

$$T \vdash \neg Smv((\mu B)(B|y)) \Rightarrow (B|\mathbf{u}_{o\alpha}) \subseteq (B|y) \&^+ SmSi((\mu B)(B|\mathbf{u}_{o\alpha})). \quad (21)$$

Using Theorem 2.3 we have

$$T \vdash Bi v((\mu B)(B|y)) \Rightarrow \neg Sm\bar{v}((\mu B)(B|y)). \quad (22)$$

Joining (21), (22) and using properties of FTT, we obtain (19).

(b) is proved analogously using Theorem 2.2(b). \square

Lemma 4.3. Let $B, A \in Form_{o\alpha}$, $x \in Form_\alpha$ be formulas and $T \vdash NSQ_{o(o\alpha)} B_{o\alpha}$. Then the following is provable:

- (a) $T \vdash (\mathbf{F}) \Rightarrow (\mathbf{S})$,
- (b) $T \vdash (\mathbf{K}) \Rightarrow (\mathbf{F})$.
- (c) $T \vdash (\mathbf{V}) \Rightarrow (\mathbf{Z})$,
- (d) $T \vdash (\mathbf{G}) \Rightarrow (\mathbf{V})$.

Proof. (a) This implication follows from (12), definition of (\mathbf{F}) and (\mathbf{S}) (Definition 4.1) and Theorem 2.2(b).

(b) After rewriting, the proposition says that

$$T \vdash (\exists y)[(\forall x)((B|y)x \Rightarrow Ax) \wedge \neg Sm\bar{v}((\mu B)(B|y))] \Rightarrow (\exists y')[(\forall x)((B|y')x \Rightarrow Ax) \wedge SmSi((\mu B)(B|y'))] \quad (23)$$

where $y, y' \in Form_{o\alpha}$, $x \in Form_\alpha$. By the assumption (17) and Theorem 2.1, we extend conservatively theory T^{IQ} by a new constant $\mathbf{u}_{o\alpha}$ and consider an arbitrary $y_{o\alpha}$. Then from $T \vdash NSQ_{o(o\alpha)} B_{o\alpha}$ we obtain

$$T \vdash \neg Sm\bar{v}((\mu B)(B|y)) \Rightarrow (B|\mathbf{u}) \subseteq (B|y) \&^+ SmSi((\mu B)(B|\mathbf{u})). \quad (24)$$

From definition of \subseteq we derive

$$T \vdash (B|\mathbf{u}) \subseteq (B|y) \Rightarrow [(\forall x)((B|y)x \Rightarrow Ax) \Rightarrow (\forall x)((B|\mathbf{u})x \Rightarrow Ax)].$$

From this and (24) we obtain

$$T \vdash \neg Sm\bar{v}((\mu B)(B|y)) \Rightarrow [(\forall x)((B|y)x \Rightarrow Ax) \Rightarrow (\forall x)((B|\mathbf{u})x \Rightarrow Ax) \wedge^+ SmSi((\mu B)(B|\mathbf{u}))] \quad (25)$$

by the properties of \mathbb{L} -FTT.

From the general property $\vdash ((A \wedge B) \Rightarrow C) \Rightarrow (A \Rightarrow (B \Rightarrow C))$ and (25) we obtain (23) using the axiom of existence, rule of generalization, the properties of quantifiers and the properties of \mathbb{L} -FTT.

(c)–(d) are proved analogously. \square

Lemma 4.4. Let $B, A \in Form_{o\alpha}$, $x \in Form_\alpha$ be formulas and $T \vdash NSQ_{o(o\alpha)} B_{o\alpha}$. Let Ev_{oo} be an arbitrary evaluative expression. Then the following is provable in T :

- (a) $T \vdash (*Q_{Ev}^\forall x)(B, A) \Rightarrow (Q_{Bi\Delta}^\exists x)(B, A)$,
- (b) $T \vdash (*Q_{Ev}^\forall x)(B, \neg A) \Rightarrow (Q_{Bi\Delta}^\exists x)(B, \neg A)$.

Proof. (a) By properties of \mathbb{L} -FTT we have

$$T \vdash ((B|z)x \Rightarrow Ax) \&(B|z)x \Rightarrow (B|z)x \wedge Ax$$

By adjunction and using the quantifiers properties we obtain

$$T \vdash (\forall x)((B|z)x \Rightarrow Ax) \&(\exists x)(B|z)x \Rightarrow (\exists x)(B|z)x \wedge Ax$$

By weakening of \wedge and using $T \vdash (B|z)x \Rightarrow Bx$ we have

$$T \vdash ((\forall x)((B|z)x \Rightarrow Ax) \&(\exists x)(B|z)x) \wedge Ev((\mu B)(B|z)) \Rightarrow (\exists x)(Bx \wedge Ax)$$

Finally by the quantifier $(\exists z)$ we conclude that

$$T \vdash (\exists z)((\forall x)((B|z)x \Rightarrow Ax) \&(\exists x)(B|z)x) \wedge Ev((\mu B)(B|z)) \Rightarrow (\exists x)(Bx \wedge Ax)$$

For specific evaluative expressions Ev , the lemma follows from Lemma 4.3.

(b) Analogously as (a). \square

Fig. 2. The relation superaltern–subaltern from the graded Peterson’s square that includes “A few” and “Several”.

Note that we cannot avoid the subformula $(\exists x)(B|z)$ in the antecedent, which means that both implications hold with the presupposition only.

On the basis of the previous lemma, we summarize monotonous behavior of intermediate quantifiers in the following theorem.

Theorem 4.5. *The following implications between intermediate quantifiers are provable in T :*

- (a) $T \vdash (A) \Rightarrow (P), T \vdash (P) \Rightarrow (T), T \vdash (T) \Rightarrow (K),$
 $T \vdash (K) \Rightarrow (F), T \vdash (F) \Rightarrow (S).$
- (b) $T \vdash (*A) \Rightarrow (I), T \vdash (*P) \Rightarrow (I), T \vdash (*T) \Rightarrow (I),$
 $T \vdash (*K) \Rightarrow (I), T \vdash (*F) \Rightarrow (I), T \vdash (*S) \Rightarrow (I).$
- (c) $T \vdash (E) \Rightarrow (B), T \vdash (B) \Rightarrow (D), T \vdash (D) \Rightarrow (G),$
 $T \vdash (G) \Rightarrow (V), T \vdash (V) \Rightarrow (Z).$
- (d) $T \vdash (*E) \Rightarrow (O), T \vdash (*B) \Rightarrow (O), T \vdash (*D) \Rightarrow (O),$
 $T \vdash (*G) \Rightarrow (O), T \vdash (*V) \Rightarrow (O), T \vdash (*Z) \Rightarrow (O).$

Proof. (a) follows from Theorem 3.10 and Lemma 4.3.

(b) follows from Lemma 4.4 by setting specific evaluative linguistic expressions for Ev .

(c)–(d) are proved analogously. \square

4.3. Discussion about the position of “Several” and “A few”

Recall from Introduction that “A few” or “Several” denote more than one or two, but less than a considerable number. These quantifiers characterize specific sizes of sets accompanied by a degree of truth. In our framework, we conceptualize size through the notion of measure, which encompasses both countable and uncountable aspects, rendering “a few” and “a little” formally indistinguishable. The question arises, what is the relation between these quantifiers.

One of the basic relations is that of *sup-sub-altern*. Classically, a formula P_2 is a *subaltern* of P_1 (P_1 is a *superaltern* of P_2) if in any model it must be true if P_1 is true. Syntactically this means that $\vdash P_1 \Rightarrow P_2$ which in fuzzy logic means that $\mathcal{M}(P_1) \leq \mathcal{M}(P_2)$ holds in any model \mathcal{M} (see, e.g., [1]).

This relation is characterized in Theorem 4.5 and depicted in Fig. 2. Note that “A few” is defined using an evaluative expression ^+SmSi that implies ^+SmVe used in the definition of “Several”. Hence, we obtain the implication $T \vdash (F) \Rightarrow (S)$ in Lemma 4.3(a). Let us emphasize that we are comparing *truth values*. For example, let us consider a context of 20 apples and let 7 of them be rotten. Then the proposition “Several apples are rotten” is true but “A few apples are rotten” is not true since “several” means more than “a few” and, therefore, 7 is not “a few” (in the given context).

However, there exists also another relation that can informally be characterized as “big (fuzzy) sets contain small ones”. For quantifiers defined using evaluative expressions $Bi v$ this works in accordance with the sub-altern relation. For example, “Most” implies “Many” (i.e., $T \Rightarrow (K)$) and also, a (fuzzy) set containing most elements of the universe has a subset containing many elements of it.

For quantifiers defined using the evaluative expression $Sm v$ this relation is reversed. With reference to the example above, since 7 apples are rotten then also 3 of them are rotten. In other words, the set of 7 apples contains the set of 3, i.e., among several rotten apples there are a few rotten ones. While the sup-sub-altern relation compares truth values, the latter relation compares (fuzzy) subsets. In our theory, the latter is assured by axiom (18).

Theorem 4.6. Let T be consistent theory in which axiom **PSQ** holds true and let \mathcal{M} be a model of T . Let $T \vdash (Q_{+SmVe}^{\forall} x_{\alpha})(B_{o\alpha}, A_{o\alpha})$ and denote $B = \mathcal{M}(B_{o\alpha}), A = \mathcal{M}(A_{o\alpha})$. Then there are fuzzy sets $Y, S \subseteq M$ such that

$$F_{+SmVe}^R(B, B|Y) > 0, B|S \subseteq B|Y \text{ and}$$

$$F_{+SmSi}^R(B, B|S) > 0.$$

Proof. Using substitution axiom, it follows from the assumption that

$$\mathcal{M}((\exists y)((\forall x)(B|y)x \Rightarrow Ax) \wedge +SmVe(\mu B)(B|y)) = 1$$

which is interpreted in \mathcal{M} as

$$\bigvee_{Y \subseteq M} \left(\bigwedge_{m \in M} ((B|Y)(m) \rightarrow A(m)) \wedge F_{+SmVe}^R(B, B|Y) \right) = 1.$$

Hence, there is a fuzzy set $Y_0 \subseteq M$ such that

$$F_{+SmVe}^R(B, B|Y) > 0 \tag{26}$$

(note that the truth value in (26) can be very close to 1). Joining (26) with the interpretation of axiom (18) we conclude that there is a fuzzy set $S \subseteq M$ such that

$$0 < [B|S \subseteq B|Y_0] \otimes F_{+SmSi}^R(B, B|Y).$$

Using Lemma 3.6(b) we obtain the theorem. \square

This theorem justifies formally in our theory the observation discussed above. Namely, if the quantifier “Several B are A ” is true then there is a model and a fuzzy subset of B that contains a few elements having the property A .

4.4. Formalization of syllogisms

4.4.1. Syllogisms and their validity

A syllogism is a type of logical argument employing deductive reasoning to reach a conclusion derived from two propositions that are asserted or assumed to be true. From a mathematical standpoint, a syllogism can be represented as a triple of related formulas $\mathcal{S} = \langle \mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{C} \rangle$ within a formal logical system.

Let $Q_{\mathcal{P}_1}, Q_{\mathcal{P}_2}, Q_{\mathcal{C}}$ be quantifier symbols introduced in (12) or (13). Let $S, P, M \in Form_{o\alpha}$ be formulas representing properties of elements of type α . The S is a *subject*, P is a *predicate*, and M is a *middle formula*. In our discussion, we will adhere to the conventions of the four standard figures.

Figure I	Figure II	Figure III	Figure IV
$\mathcal{P}_1: Q_{\mathcal{P}_1} M \text{ are } P$	$\mathcal{P}_1: Q_{\mathcal{P}_1} P \text{ are } M$	$\mathcal{P}_1: Q_{\mathcal{P}_1} M \text{ are } P$	$\mathcal{P}_1: Q_{\mathcal{P}_1} P \text{ are } M$
$\mathcal{P}_2: Q_{\mathcal{P}_2} S \text{ are } M$	$\mathcal{P}_2: Q_{\mathcal{P}_2} S \text{ are } M$	$\mathcal{P}_2: Q_{\mathcal{P}_2} M \text{ are } S$	$\mathcal{P}_2: Q_{\mathcal{P}_2} M \text{ are } S$
$\mathcal{C}: Q_{\mathcal{C}} S \text{ are } P$			

The proposition \mathcal{P}_1 is a *major premise*, \mathcal{P}_2 is a *minor premise* and \mathcal{C} is a *conclusion*. If all $Q_{\mathcal{P}_1}, Q_{\mathcal{P}_2}, Q_{\mathcal{C}} \in \{\forall, \exists\}$ then the corresponding syllogism is classical.

In accordance with the tradition, we will refer to quantifiers using the bold-face letters introduced in Section 3 and the syllogisms are referred to using triples of them. For example, **AAA**-I denotes the syllogism

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{Figure I} \\ A: \text{All } M \text{ are } P \\ A: \text{All } S \text{ are } M \\ \hline A: \text{All } S \text{ are } P \end{array}$$

Definition 4.7. Let $\mathcal{S} = \langle \mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{C} \rangle$ be a syllogism. It is *valid* if

$$\mathcal{M}(\mathcal{P}_1) \otimes \mathcal{M}(\mathcal{P}_2) \leq \mathcal{M}(\mathcal{C})$$

holds in any model $\mathcal{M} \models T^{IQ}$. By the completeness theorem [24], this syntactically means that $T^{IQ} \vdash \mathcal{P}_1 \ \& \ \mathcal{P}_2 \Rightarrow \mathcal{C}$.

We can also consider a weaker definition of validity (cf. [4]): \mathcal{S} is valid in a theory T if $T \vdash \mathcal{P}_1$ and $T \vdash \mathcal{P}_2$ imply that $T \vdash \mathcal{C}$. Obviously, validity in the sense of Definition 4.7 implies weak validity.

4.4.2. Presupposition by existential import

When analyzing logical syllogisms, logicians found that some syllogisms can be valid only if we assume that the universe of quantification is non-empty. Such an assumption is natural for medieval logicians. The logical formalism, however, does not contain it without adding the formula $(\exists x)Sx$. Example of such a syllogism is **AAI-I** of Figure I. Its direct formalization is a formula $((\forall x)(Mx \Rightarrow \neg Px) \& (\forall x)(Sx \Rightarrow Mx) \Rightarrow (\exists x)(Sx \wedge \neg Px))$ which is not valid. However, if we add subformula $(\exists x)S$ then we can prove

$$T^{1Q} \vdash ((\forall x)(Mx \Rightarrow Px) \& [(\forall x)(Sx \Rightarrow Mx) \& (\exists x)Sx]) \Rightarrow (\exists x)(Sx \wedge Px) \quad (27)$$

which is a formula representing the syllogism **A*AI-I** where $*A$ is the subformula of (27) in the square brackets.

The necessity to add subformula $(\exists x)S$ is called *presupposition by existential import*.⁴ In general, a *presupposition* is something that one assumes to be true to continue with further reasoning. In our theory, we include presupposition inside the formula representing the quantifier — see (14) and (15).

Note that presupposition rises from the algebraic analysis of syllogisms (cf. [25]). Namely, there is no residuated lattice such that $a \rightarrow b \leq a \wedge b$, $a, b \in E$ but in any BL-algebra and, consequently, also in any MV-algebra the following holds true:

$$a \otimes (a \rightarrow b) = a \wedge b. \quad (28)$$

A deep algebraic analysis reveals that (28) stands behind the validity of (27) (cf. [25]).

The presupposition is also necessary for some syllogisms of Figures I, II, IV, and most of Figure III. There are four syllogisms of Figure III that are valid without presupposition, namely **IAI**, **AII**, **OAo**, **EIO** (cf. [7]). Their validity is based on the provable algebraic inequality

$$(b \rightarrow c) \otimes (a \wedge b) \leq a \wedge c. \quad (29)$$

All the other syllogisms of this figure require presupposition. If we compare (28) and (29), we can see that the algebraic core for the necessity of the presupposition lies in the occurrence of join $a \wedge c$ on the right side of the corresponding algebraic inequality. It is unnecessary only if join occurs also on its left side (as is the case of (29)).

When interpreting (27) in a model $\mathcal{M} \vDash T^{1Q}$, we immediately see that it is trivially true if $\mathcal{M}_p((\exists x)Sx) = 0$. Hence, there are models in which the fuzzy set S can be empty. On the other hand, this cannot happen if we consider the weaker concept of validity mentioned in the previous subsection. Then $\mathcal{M}_p((\exists x)Sx) = 1$ and so, S is non-empty.⁵

A slightly more complicated situation occurs for non-trivial syllogisms of Figure III. Validity of them is based on the provable formula

$$T^{1Q} \vdash [(\forall x)((M|z)x \Rightarrow Px) \& (\forall x)((M|z')x \Rightarrow Sx)] \Rightarrow [(\exists x)((M|z)x \& (M|z')x)] \Rightarrow (\exists x)(Sx \wedge Px). \quad (30)$$

The subformula $(\exists x)((M|z)x \& (M|z')x)$ has a similar role as the subformula $(\exists x)Sx$ above and we will call it *common presupposition*, or *common existential import*. It means that (30) is non-trivially true in a model \mathcal{M} if for some assignment p the strong intersection $\mathcal{M}_p(M|z) \wp \mathcal{M}_p(M|z') \neq \emptyset$.

From the algebraic point of view, the common presupposition rises from the provable inequality

$$(a \otimes b) \otimes (b \rightarrow d) \otimes (a \rightarrow c) \leq c \wedge d.$$

In the sequel, we will denote propositions with common presupposition by $*(\mathcal{P}_1 \& \mathcal{P}_2)$.

In the following two sections we will introduce and syntactically analyze intermediate syllogisms with new “small” quantifiers. First, we will look in detail at Figures-I, II, IV, where the proofs of logical syllogisms are based on the assumption that at least one of the premises contains the classical universal quantifier \forall . Section 6 will be devoted to the third figure. Recall that by T , we denote a consistent extension of the theory T^{1Q} in which axiom (17) holds for the corresponding universe of quantification, and it contains regular formulas $B \in Form_{o\alpha}$.

5. Extended intermediate syllogisms of Figures I, II, IV

It is specific for valid syllogisms of Figures I, II, and IV that at least one of the premises must be universal. Lemma 3.12(e) explains why this is necessary. Namely, the given premise is universal if the evaluative expression $Bi\Delta$ is used. Then the corresponding universe of quantification M or P is contained in the other one. Hence, it must intersect with the third universe independently of the second quantifier. Consequently, the corresponding syllogism is valid.

⁴ To simplify the presentation, we will usually speak about presupposition, or existential import.

⁵ Note that in fuzzy logic, this *does not mean* that there is an element $m \in M$ such that $\mathcal{M}_p(S)(m) = 1$!

5.1. Extended intermediate syllogisms of Figure-I-affirmative

Theorem 5.1. *The syllogisms AFF, ASS of Figure-I are valid in T.*

Proof. The syllogisms can be formally written as follows:

$$\text{AFF-I: } \frac{(\forall x)(Mx \Rightarrow Px) \quad (\exists z)((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Mx) \wedge (+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z)))}{(\exists z)((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Px) \wedge (+SmSi)((\mu S)z))}$$

By the properties of quantifiers and the properties of \mathbb{L} -FTT we can prove

$$T \vdash (\forall x)(Mx \Rightarrow Px) \Rightarrow ((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Mx) \Rightarrow (\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Px)).$$

By property⁶ we obtain that

$$T \vdash (\forall x)(Mx \Rightarrow Px) \Rightarrow \{((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Mx) \wedge (+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z))) \Rightarrow ((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Px) \wedge (+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z)))\}. \quad (31)$$

Finally, by the rule of generalization with respect to $(\forall z)$ and by the properties of \mathbb{L} -FTT we obtain

$$T \vdash (\forall x)(Mx \Rightarrow Px) \& (\exists z)((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Mx) \wedge (+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z))) \Rightarrow (\exists z)((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Px) \wedge (+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z))).$$

We can conclude that by putting $(+SmSi)$ instead of $(+SmVe)$ we obtain valid syllogism ASS-I. \square

Theorem 5.2. *The syllogisms A*AI, A*PI, A*TI, A*KI, A*FI, A*SI of Figure-I are valid in T.*

Proof. Let $E_v = \{Bi\Delta, BiEx, BiVe, \neg Sm\bar{v}, +SmSi, +SmVe\}$. Then syllogisms can be formally written as follows:

$$\frac{(\forall x)(Mx \Rightarrow Px) \quad (\exists z)((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Mx) \& (\exists x)((S|z)x) \wedge (Ev((\mu S)(S|z))))}{(\exists x)(Sx \wedge Px)}$$

By the properties of quantifiers and the properties of \mathbb{L} -FTT we can prove

$$T^{IQ} \vdash (Mx \Rightarrow Px) \& ((S|z)x \Rightarrow Mx) \Rightarrow ((S|z)x \Rightarrow Px) \quad (32)$$

By $T^{IQ} \vdash ((S|z)x \Rightarrow Px) \Rightarrow ((S|z)x \Rightarrow ((S|z)x \wedge Px))$ by (32) and using the transitivity we have

$$T^{IQ} \vdash ((Mx \Rightarrow Px) \& ((S|z)x \Rightarrow Px)) \Rightarrow ((S|z)x \Rightarrow ((S|z)x \wedge Px)) \quad (33)$$

which is equivalent with

$$T^{IQ} \vdash (((Mx \Rightarrow Px) \& ((S|z)x \Rightarrow Px)) \& ((S|z)x) \Rightarrow ((S|z)x \wedge Px)) \quad (34)$$

By $\vdash (S|z)x \Rightarrow Sx$, hence $\vdash ((S|z)x \wedge Px) \Rightarrow (Sx \wedge Px)$ and using the transitivity we obtain

$$T^{IQ} \vdash ((Mx \Rightarrow Px) \& ((S|z)x \Rightarrow Px)) \Rightarrow ((S|z)x) \Rightarrow (Sx \wedge Px)$$

By quantifiers properties and properties of \mathbb{L} -FTT we have

$$T^{IQ} \vdash ((\forall x)(Mx \Rightarrow Px) \& (\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Px)) \Rightarrow (\exists x)((S|z)x) \Rightarrow (\exists x)(Sx \wedge Px)$$

By weakening of \wedge , using adjunction and by quantifiers properties we conclude that

$$T \vdash ((\forall x)(Mx \Rightarrow Px) \& (\exists z)[(\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Px) \& (\exists x)((S|z)x) \wedge Ev((\mu S)(S|z))]) \Rightarrow (\exists x)(Sx \wedge Px) \quad (35)$$

By putting of the concrete evaluative linguistic expressions we obtain the valid syllogisms A*AI, A*PI, A*TI, A*KI, A*FI, A*SI. For example, by putting $E_v = +Sm$ we have the syllogism A*FI-I. \square

Note that for formal reasons, we must assume presupposition also for the quantifiers F, S though their definition contains the assumption of non-emptiness.

The following theorem presents all affirmative logical syllogisms of the first figure with seven intermediate quantifiers.

Note that if the corresponding syllogism does not contain the quantifiers F, V, S, Z then it is valid just in T^{IQ} , otherwise the property (17) is required.

⁶ If $T \vdash A \Rightarrow (B \Rightarrow C)$ then $T \vdash A \Rightarrow ((B \wedge D) \Rightarrow (C \wedge D))$ see the proof in [7] Lemma 1(b).

In the theorems below, we will present an overview of the valid syllogisms organized in **triangles** that are ordered according to the relation superaltern–subaltern: up-down in the conclusion and left-right in the second premise. Hence, if a syllogism is valid then all syllogisms standing below, or to the right, are also valid. For more detailed description of this property in view of the position of these quantifiers, we refer the reader to previous publications (see [19,26]).

Theorem 5.3. *The following syllogisms of Figure-I are valid in T:*

super	(AAA)						
super	AAP	(APP)					
super	AAT	APT	(ATT)				
super	AAK	APK	ATK	(AKK)			
sub	AAF	APF	ATF	AKF	(AFF)		
super	AAS	APS	ATS	AKS	AFS	(ASS)	
sub	A*AI	A*PI	A*TI	A*KI	A*FI	A*SI	(AII)

Proof. Validity of logical syllogisms **AFF**, **ASS-I** was proved in Theorem 5.1. Validity of **AAA**, **APP**, **ATT**, **AKK**, **AAP**, **AAT**, **AAK-I**, **APT**, **APK**, **ATK-I** was proved in [7]. Let us recall that it was proved analogously to validity of the syllogisms **AFF**, **ASS-I** in Theorem 5.1. Validity of **A*AI**, **A*PI**, **A*TI**, **A*KI**, **A*FI**, **A*SI** was proved in Theorem 5.2.

Using the monotonicity, we can prove validity of the other syllogisms. From the validity of syllogisms **AAK**, **APK**, **ATK**, **AKK**, **AFF-I** using Theorem 4.5(a) we obtain validity of syllogisms **AAF**, **APF**, **ATF**, **AKF**, **AFS-I**, respectively. Analogously, from this group of valid syllogisms, we obtain validity of syllogisms **AAS**, **APS**, **ATS**, **AKS-I** in the theory T. □

5.2. Extended intermediate syllogisms of Figure-I-negative

Theorem 5.4. *Syllogisms **EFV**, **ESZ** of Figure-I are valid in T.*

Proof. The syllogisms can be formally written as follows:

$$\text{EFV-I: } \frac{(\forall x)(Mx \Rightarrow \neg Px) \quad (\exists z)((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Mx) \wedge (^+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z)))}{(\exists z)((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow \neg Px) \wedge (^+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z)))}$$

By the properties of quantifiers and the properties of L-FTT we can prove

$$T \vdash (\forall x)(Mx \Rightarrow \neg Px) \Rightarrow ((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Mx) \Rightarrow (\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow \neg Px)).$$

Analogously by the same property as in Theorem 5.1 we obtain that

$$T \vdash (\forall x)(Mx \Rightarrow \neg Px) \Rightarrow \{((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Mx) \wedge (^+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z))) \Rightarrow ((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow \neg Px) \wedge (^+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z)))\}. \quad (36)$$

Finally, by the rule of generalization with respect to (∀z) and by the properties of L-FTT we obtain

$$T \vdash (\forall x)(Mx \Rightarrow \neg Px) \& (\exists z)((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Mx) \wedge (^+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z))) \Rightarrow (\exists z)((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow \neg Px) \wedge (^+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z)))$$

which is syllogism **EFV-I**. By putting (⁺SmSi) instead of (⁺SmVe) we obtain validity of syllogism **ESZ-I**. □

Theorem 5.5. *The syllogisms **E*AO**, **E*PO**, **E*TO**, **E*KO**, **E*FO**, **E*SO** of Figure-I are valid in T.*

Proof. Let $E_v = \{Bi\Delta, BiEx, BiVe, \neg Sm\bar{v}, ^+SmSi, ^+SmVe\}$. Then syllogisms can be formally written as follows:

$$\frac{(\forall x)(Mx \Rightarrow \neg Px) \quad (\exists z)((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Mx) \& (\exists x)((S|z)x) \wedge (E_v)((\mu S)(S|z)))}{(\exists x)(Sx \wedge \neg Px)}$$

The proof can be constructed analogously as the proof of Theorem 5.2. □

Theorem 5.6. *The following syllogisms of Figure-I are valid in T:*

super	(EAE)						
super	EAB	(EPB)					
super	EAD	EPD	(ETD)				
super	EAG	EPG	ETG	(EKG)			
sub	EAV	EPV	ETD	EKV	(EFV)		
super	EAZ	EPZ	ETZ	EKZ	EFV	(ESZ)	
sub	E*AO	E*PO	E*TO	E*KO	E*FO	E*SO	(EIO)

Proof. Validity of logical syllogisms **EFV**, **ESZ** was proved in Theorem 5.5. Validity of syllogisms **EAE**, **EPB**, **ETD**, **EKG**, **EAB**, **EAD**, **EAG**, **EPD**, **EPG**, **ETG**-I was proved in [7]. Validity of logical syllogisms with particular conclusion **E*AO**, **E*PO**, **E*TO**, **E*KO** was proved in Theorem 5.5. Using the monotonicity, we are able to prove validity of the other negative syllogisms. From validity of **EAG**, **EPG**, **ETG**, **EKG**, **EFV**-I we obtain validity of syllogisms **EAV**, **EPV**, **ETV**, **EKV**, **EFZ**-I, respectively using Theorem 4.5(c). Analogously, from these valid groups of syllogisms we obtain validity of syllogisms **EAZ**, **EPZ**, **ETZ**, **EKZ**-I. \square

5.3. Extended intermediate syllogisms of Figure-II-negative

Theorem 5.7. *Syllogisms AVV, AZZ of Figure-II are valid in T.*

Proof. The syllogisms can be formally written as follows:

$$\text{AVV-II: } \frac{(\forall x)(Px \Rightarrow Mx) \quad (\exists z)((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow \neg Mx) \wedge (+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z)))}{(\exists z)((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow \neg Px) \wedge (+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z)))}$$

By the properties of quantifiers and the properties of \mathbb{L} -FTT we can prove that

$$T \vdash (\forall x)(Px \Rightarrow Mx) \Rightarrow ((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow \neg Mx) \Rightarrow (\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow \neg Px)).$$

Analogously by the same property as in Theorem 5.1 we obtain that

$$T \vdash (\forall x)(Px \Rightarrow Mx) \Rightarrow \{((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow \neg Mx) \wedge (+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z))) \Rightarrow ((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow \neg Px) \wedge (+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z)))\}. \quad (37)$$

Finally, by the rule of generalization with respect to $(\forall z)$ and by properties of \mathbb{L} -FTT we obtain

$$T \vdash (\forall x)(Px \Rightarrow Mx) \& (\exists z)((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow \neg Mx) \wedge (+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z))) \Rightarrow (\exists z)((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow \neg Px) \wedge (+SmSi)((\mu S)(S|z))).$$

We can conclude that by putting $(+SmSi)$ instead of $(+SmVe)$ we obtain the valid syllogism **AZZ**. \square

Theorem 5.8. *The syllogisms*

- (a) **A*EO**, **A*BO**, **A*DO**, **A*GO**, **A*VO**, **A*ZO** of Figure-II are valid in T.
- (b) **E*AO**, **E*PO**, **E*TO**, **E*KO**, **E*FO**, **E*SO** of Figure-II are valid in T.

Proof. (a) Let $Ev = \{Bi\Delta, BiEx, BiVe, \neg Sm\bar{v}, +SmSi, +SmVe\}$. Then syllogisms can be formally written as follows:

$$\frac{(\forall x)(Px \Rightarrow Mx) \quad (\exists z)((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow \neg Mx) \& (\exists x)((S|z)x) \wedge (Ev((\mu S)(S|z))))}{(\exists x)(Sx \wedge \neg Px)}$$

The validity of the group of syllogisms is based on the following provable formula:

$$T \vdash ((\forall x)(Px \Rightarrow Mx) \& (\exists z)[(\forall x)(Sx \Rightarrow \neg Mx) \& (\exists x)((S|z)x) \wedge Ev((\mu S)(S|z))]) \Rightarrow (\exists x)(Sx \wedge \neg Px) \quad (38)$$

The proof can be constructed analogously as the proof of Theorem 5.2.

(b) Let $Ev = \{Bi\Delta, BiEx, BiVe, \neg Sm\bar{v}, +SmSi, +SmVe\}$. The syllogisms can be formally written as follows:

$$\frac{(\forall x)(Px \Rightarrow \neg Mx) \quad (\exists z)((\forall x)((S|z)x \Rightarrow Mx) \& (\exists x)((S|z)x) \wedge (Ev((\mu S)(S|z))))}{(\exists x)(Sx \wedge \neg Px).$$

The proof can be constructed analogously as the proof of (a). \square

Theorem 5.9. *The following syllogisms of Figure-II are valid in T:*

- super **(AEE)**
- super **AEB** **(ABB)**
- super **AED** **ABD** **(ADD)**
- super **AEG** **ABG** **ADG** **(AGG)**
- sub **AEV** **ABV** **ADD** **AGV** **(AVV)**
- super **AEZ** **ABZ** **ADZ** **AGZ** **AVV** **(AZZ)**
- super **A*EO** **A*BO** **A*DO** **A*GO** **A*VO** **A*ZO** **(AOO)**

Proof. Validity of syllogisms **AVV, AZZ-II** was proved in Theorem 5.7. Validity of syllogisms **AEE, ABB, ADD, AGG, AEB, AED, AEG, ABD, ABG, ADG-II** was proved in [7]. The validity of the syllogisms with particular conclusion **A*EO, A*BO, A*DO, A*GO-II** was proved in Theorem 5.8(a). Using the monotonicity, we are able to prove validity of the other negative syllogisms. From the validity of the negative syllogisms **AEG, ABG, ADG, AGG, AVV-II** using Theorem 4.5(c) we obtain the validity of syllogisms **AEV, EBV, ADV, AGV, AVZ-II**, respectively. Analogously, from this group of valid syllogisms we obtain validity of the syllogisms **AEZ, ABZ, ADZ, AGZ-II**. \square

Theorem 5.10. *The following syllogisms of Figure-II are valid in T:*

- super **(EAE)**
- super **EAB** **(EPB)**
- super **EAD** **EPD** **(ETD)**
- super **EAG** **EPG** **ETG** **(EKG)**
- sub **EAV** **EPV** **ETV** **EKV** **(EFV)**
- super **EAZ** **EPZ** **ETZ** **EKZ** **EFZ** **(ESZ)**
- sub **E*AO** **E*PO** **E*TO** **E*KO** **E*FO** **E*SO** **(EOO)**

Proof. Analogously as in Theorem 5.9. \square

5.4. Extended intermediate syllogisms of Figure-IV

Theorem 5.11. *The following syllogisms of Figure-IV are valid in T:*

<i>super</i>	*AAI	(AEE)	E*AO
<i>super</i>	*PAI	AEB	E*PO
<i>super</i>	*TAI	AED	E*TO
<i>super</i>	*KAI	AEG	E*KO
<i>sub</i>	*FAI	AEV	E*FO
<i>super</i>	*SAI	AEZ	E*SO
<i>sub</i>	(IAI)	(AEO)	(EIO)

Proof. Syllogisms circled in bold are the classical Aristotle ones. Let **IAI**-IV be valid in T^{IQ} . Then $T^{IQ} \vdash \mathbf{I} \Rightarrow (\mathbf{A} \Rightarrow \mathbf{I})$. By Theorem 4.5(b) and by the property of transitivity we obtain $T \vdash \mathbf{S} \Rightarrow (\mathbf{A} \Rightarrow \mathbf{I})$. It leads to validity of the syllogism *SAI-IV. Obviously applying Theorem 4.5(b) we are able to prove the validity other syllogisms in the first column.

The validity of syllogism AEE-IV, after application of Theorem 4.5(c) gives us validity of the group of syllogisms AEB, AED, AEG, AEV, AEZ-IV. Furthermore, let EIO-IV be valid in T^{IQ} . Then we know $T^{IQ} \vdash \mathbf{E} \Rightarrow (\mathbf{I} \Rightarrow \mathbf{O})$ and immediately $T^{IQ} \vdash \mathbf{I} \Rightarrow (\mathbf{E} \Rightarrow \mathbf{O})$. By following the same steps as in the first column using Theorem 4.5(b) we conclude that E*PO, E*TO, E*KO, E*FO, E*SO-IV are valid in T . \square

6. Extended intermediate syllogisms of Figure-III

6.1. Figure III enforces presupposition

We will show that except for syllogisms **IAI**, **AII**, **OAo**, **EIO**, all the other syllogisms of Figure III cannot be valid without considering the common presupposition discussed in Subsection 4.4.2. Namely, formula (39) below is the universal formula expressing the validity of all the syllogisms of Figure III.

Lemma 6.1. Let M_{oa} be a formula of T^{IQ} and $z, z' \in \text{Form}_{oa}$, $x \in \text{Form}_a$ be variables. Then the following is provable:

$$T^{IQ} \vdash [(\exists z)(\exists z')[(\forall x)((M|z)x \Rightarrow Px) \wedge Ev((\mu M)(M|z))] \& (\forall x)((M|z')x \Rightarrow Sx) \wedge Ev'((\mu M)(M|z'))] \& (\exists x)((M|z)x \& (M|z')x)] \Rightarrow (\exists x)(Sx \wedge Px) \quad (39)$$

where Ev, Ev' are arbitrary evaluative expressions.

Proof. We start with the provable formula

$$T \vdash (((M|z)x \Rightarrow Px) \& ((M|z')x \Rightarrow Sx)) \Rightarrow (((M|z)x \& (M|z')x) \Rightarrow (Sx \wedge Px)).$$

By the properties of \mathbb{L} -FTT we obtain

$$T \vdash ((\forall x)((M|z)x \Rightarrow Px) \& (\forall x)((M|z')x \Rightarrow Sx)) \Rightarrow (((\exists x)((M|z)x \& (M|z')x)) \Rightarrow (\exists x)(Sx \wedge Px)) \quad (40)$$

By weakening of \wedge , applying of $T \vdash (A \Rightarrow (B \Rightarrow C)) \equiv (A \& B) \Rightarrow C$) and using transitivity we have

$$T \vdash [(\forall x)((M|z)x \Rightarrow Px) \wedge Ev((\mu M)(M|z))] \& ((\forall x)((M|z')x \Rightarrow Sx) \wedge Ev'((\mu M)(M|z')) \& (\exists x)((M|z)x \& (M|z')x)] \Rightarrow (\exists x)(Sx \wedge Px) \quad (41)$$

Finally by the quantifier properties with respect to z and z' we obtain (39) using the rules of \mathbb{L} -FTT. \square

The following lemma says that fuzzy subsets having “sufficiently big” measure necessarily have non-empty intersection.

Lemma 6.2. Let M_{oa} be a formula of T^{IQ} , $z, z' \in \text{Form}_{oa}$, $x \in \text{Form}_a$ be variables, $Ev, Ev' \in \{\text{BiEx}, \text{BiVe}, \neg(\text{Sm}\bar{v})\}$. Then

$$T \vdash (\exists z)(\exists z') \Delta [Ev((\mu M)(M|z)) \& Ev'((\mu M)(M|z')) \& (\exists x)((M|z)x \& (M|z')x)] \quad (42)$$

Proof. See the proof of [7, Lemma 3]. \square

6.2. Syllogisms of Figure-III with a universal premise

If a syllogism contains a universal premise, then the common presupposition reduces to the ordinary one, as seen from the proof of the following theorem.

Theorem 6.3. *The following affirmative syllogisms of Figure-III are valid in T .*

$$\begin{array}{cccccc} \textcircled{*AAI} & *PAI & *TAI & *KAI & *FAI & *SAI & \textcircled{IAI} \\ A*PI & A*TI & A*KI & A*FI & A*SI & \textcircled{AII} \end{array}$$

Proof. Validity of classical syllogisms $*AAI, IAI, AII$ -III was syntactically proved in [7]. In [19, Theorem 6] we proved that

$$T^{IQ} \vdash Q_{Bi\Delta}^{\forall}(M, P) \equiv (\forall x)(Mx \Rightarrow Px).$$

If in (39) we substitute $Ev := Bi\Delta$, we obtain $T^{IQ} \vdash (Bi\Delta)(\mu M)(M|M)$ and $T^{IQ} \vdash (M|M) \equiv M$ by [19, Lemma 8]. Consequently,

$$T^{IQ} \vdash (\exists x)((M|M)x \& (M|z')x) \equiv (\exists x)(M|z')x.$$

From this and (39) follows validity of $A*KI, A*TI, A*PI, *KAI, *TAI, *PAI$ in T^{IQ} . Since $T^{IQ} \subseteq T$, we also obtain validity of syllogisms $*SAI, A*SI, A*FI$ in T . \square

Theorem 6.3 has also an alternative proof using Theorem 4.5. Namely, from $T^{IQ} \vdash I \Rightarrow (A \Rightarrow I)$ we get $T \vdash *S \Rightarrow (A \Rightarrow I)$, which is validity of $*SAI$ -III in T . Similarly we obtain also validity of $A*SI, A*FI, *FAI$ in T , and validity of $A*KI, A*TI, A*PI, *KAI, *TAI, *PAI$ in T^{IQ} .

Taking into account validity of classical syllogisms EAO, OAO, EIO -III proved in [7], we analogously obtain also proof of the following theorem for negative syllogisms of Figure III.

Theorem 6.4. *The following negative syllogisms of Figure-III are valid in T .*

$$\begin{array}{cccccc} \textcircled{*EAO} & *BAO & *DAO & *GAO & *FVO & *ZAO & \textcircled{OAO} \\ E*PO & E*TO & E*KO & E*FO & E*SO & \textcircled{EIO} \end{array}$$

6.3. Motivation and discussion about non-trivial syllogisms of Figure III

Non-trivial syllogisms contain both premises with general intermediate quantifiers. To illustrate how syllogisms generally work, we will use Venn diagrams and follow Peterson’s discussion in [23]. He assigned individual intermediate quantifiers their approximate percentage meaning. For example, he characterized the quantifier “Most” by a percentage of “at least 60%”. The particular quantifier “Some” expresses “at least one”.

Let us assume that M consists of one hundred objects, i.e., $|M| = 100$ and consider syllogism TTI -III:

$$\begin{array}{r} \text{T: Most } M\text{'s are } P \quad (Q_{BiVe}^{\forall} x)(M, P) \\ \text{T: Most } M\text{'s are } S \quad (Q_{BiVe}^{\forall} x)(M, S) \\ \hline \text{I: Some } S \text{ are } P \quad (Q_{Bi\Delta}^{\exists} x)(S, P) \end{array}$$

If both the first as well as the second premises are true then, using percents, at least 60% of M 's have a property P and at least 60% of M 's have a property S . Using Venn’s diagram we obtain

We conclude that at least one of S 's is also P , which is the classical quantifier “Some”. In general, a valid non-trivial syllogism requires the size of the measure interpreting intermediate quantifiers in both premises to be large enough to assure non-empty Łukasiewicz intersection of the fuzzy sets corresponding to S and P .

Another example is the syllogism **FPI**:

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{FPI-III} \\ \text{A few } M \text{ are } P \\ \text{Almost all } M \text{ are } S \\ \hline \text{Some } S \text{ are } P \end{array}$$

Using Venn diagram, we can demonstrate that there is a model in which this syllogism is *not true*:

We can observe that the quantifiers “A few M are P ” and “Almost all M are S ” refer to parts of M having no common elements. Therefore, the conclusion “Some S are P ” is empty. The syllogism is not true in this model and, hence, not valid.

6.4. Validity of non-trivial syllogisms of Figure-III

The validity of non-trivial syllogisms is determined by the provability of the formula (39). However, we must take into account the common presupposition

$$(\exists x)((M|z)x \& (M|z')x)$$

whose truth value in a model can be equal to 0; hence, the truth value of a given syllogism is trivially equal to 1. This is uninteresting.

Definition 6.5. A syllogism of Figure III is *non-trivially true* for the given evaluative expressions Ev, Ev' if in any model $\mathcal{M} \models T^{IQ}$ and for any assignment $p \in \text{Asg}(\mathcal{M})$, if $\mathcal{M}_p(Ev((\mu M)(M|z))) > 0$ and $\mathcal{M}_p(Ev'((\mu M)(M|z'))) > 0$ for some formulas (fuzzy sets) $M, z, z' \in \text{Form}_{\alpha}$ then the formula for the common presupposition has non-zero truth value, i.e.

$$\mathcal{M}_p((\exists x)((M|z)x \& (M|z')x)) > 0. \tag{43}$$

Theorem 6.6.

- (a) Syllogisms $*(TT)I, *(PP)I, *(PT)I, *(TP)I$ of Figure III are non-trivially true.
- (b) Syllogisms $*(BP)O, *(DP)O, *(BT)O, *(DT)O$ of Figure III are non-trivially true.

Proof. (a) By putting concrete evaluative linguistic expressions $Ex Bi, Bi Ve$ into (39), we obtain syllogisms $*(TT)I, *(PP)I, *(PT)I, *(TP)I$. Let $\mathcal{M} \models T^{IQ}$ be a model, p an assignment, $M, z, z' \in \text{Form}_{\alpha}$ and $Ev := Bi v_1, Ev' := Bi v_2$ for some hedges v_1, v_2 . Then it follows from [20, Lemma 8(a)] and the definition of $Bi v$ that $\mathcal{M}_p(Bi v_1((\mu M)(M|z))) > 0, \mathcal{M}_p(Bi v_2((\mu M)(M|z'))) > 0$ necessarily implies that both $\mathcal{M}_p((\mu M)(M|z)) > \mathcal{M}(\dagger)$ as well as $\mathcal{M}_p((\mu M)(M|z')) > \mathcal{M}(\dagger)$ and, hence, (43) holds in any model \mathcal{M} by Lemma 3.12(b). The syllogisms in (a) are obtained by putting $v_1 := Ve$ or $v_2 := Ex$ in the respective combinations.

(b) is proved analogously. \square

Theorem 6.7. Let $T^{Ev} \vdash \neg c_{Sm\bar{v}} < a_{BiEx}$. Then syllogism $*(KP)I$ of Figure-III is non-trivially true.

Proof. Let $\mathcal{M} \models T^{Ev}$ and assume that $\mathcal{M}_p(\neg(Sm\bar{v})(\mu M)(M|z)) > 0$ and $\mathcal{M}_p((BiEx)(\mu(M)(M|z'))) > 0$ for some assignment p and $M, z, z' \in \text{Form}_{\alpha}$. By the definition of evaluation using the measure μ , this means that $\mathcal{M}_p((\mu M)(M|z)) > \mathcal{M}_p(a_{Sm\bar{v}})$ and $\mathcal{M}_p((\mu M)(M|z')) > \mathcal{M}_p(a_{BiEx})$. But $\mathcal{M}_p(a_{Sm\bar{v}}) = \mathcal{M}_p(c_{Sm\bar{v}})$ (cf. Fig. 1).

We require that

$$\mathcal{M}_p(c_{Sm\bar{v}}) \otimes \mathcal{M}_p(a_{BiEx}) > 0. \tag{44}$$

By the definition of the meaning of $\neg Sm\bar{v}, BiEx$ and the properties of measure, (44) holds if

$$\neg \mathcal{M}_p(c_{Sm\bar{v}}) = \mathcal{M}_p(\neg c_{Sm\bar{v}}) < \mathcal{M}_p(a_{BiEx}). \tag{45}$$

By Lemma 3.12(a), we conclude that $\mathcal{M}_p(M|z) \otimes \mathcal{M}_p(M|z') \neq \emptyset$. Therefore, (43) holds in any model \mathcal{M} . \square

The condition of this theorem says that the width of the support of the extension of the evaluative expression $BiEx$ is smaller than the width of the kernel of $Sm\bar{v}$ (see Fig. 1). Such an assumption seems natural, but the axioms of T^{Ev} do not imply it.

Corollary 6.8. *Under the assumptions of Theorem 6.7, syllogisms * (PK)I, * (BK)O, * (KB)O of Figure III are non-trivially true.*

7. Conclusion

We have introduced intermediate quantifiers representing a small part of the universe discourse. We have formally verified the validity of new forms of logical syllogisms in the main four figures. The first, second, and fourth figures always require at least one universal quantifier; therefore, verifying the validity of the syllogisms of these figures is more or less straightforward. More interesting is the third figure and its non-trivial syllogisms. We paid a more detailed attention to them and discussed the importance of the common presupposition for validity of the corresponding syllogisms. Our further research will be focused on study of non-trivial syllogisms in connection with the graded Peterson's square of opposition. Furthermore, we will turn our attention to non-monotonic reasoning in which intermediate quantifiers occur. We are going to show that in the presence of the latter, no contradiction following from non-monotonicity arises.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Petra Murinová: Writing – original draft. **Vilém Novák:** Validation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

Acknowledgement

This article has been produced with the financial support of the project “Research of Excellence on Digital Technologies and Wellbeing CZ.02.01.01/00/22-008/0004583” which is co-financed by the European Union.

The article has also been supported by The Polish National Agency for Academic Exchange Strategic Partnership Programme under Grant No. BPI/PST/2021/1/00031

References

- [1] P. Murinová, V. Novák, Analysis of generalized square of opposition with intermediate quantifiers, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 242 (2014) 89–113.
- [2] P. Murinová, V. Novák, The structure of generalized intermediate syllogisms, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 247 (2014) 18–37.
- [3] P. Murinová, V. Novák, Syllogisms and 5-square of opposition with intermediate quantifiers in fuzzy natural logic, *Log. Univers.* 10 (2) (2016) 339–357.
- [4] V. Novák, A formal theory of intermediate quantifiers, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 159 (10) (2008) 1229–1246.
- [5] V. Novák, P. Murinová, On the properties of measure in the theory of intermediate quantifiers and the quantifier “many”, in: *Proc. SSCI-FOCI 2017, Honolulu, USA, 2017*.
- [6] L.A. Zadeh, A computational approach to fuzzy quantifiers in natural languages, *Comput. Math.* 9 (1983) 149–184.
- [7] P. Murinová, V. Novák, A formal theory of generalized intermediate syllogisms, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 186 (2013) 47–80.
- [8] D. Dubois, H. Prade, On fuzzy syllogisms, *Comput. Intell.* 4 (1988) 171–179.
- [9] D. Dubois, L. Godo, H. López de Mántras, R. Prade, Qualitative reasoning with imprecise probabilities, *J. Intell. Inf. Syst.* 2 (1993) 319–363.
- [10] M. Pereira-Fariña, F. Díaz-Hermida, A. Bugarín, On the analysis of set-based fuzzy quantified reasoning using classical syllogistics, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 214 (2013) 83–94.
- [11] M. Pereira-Fariña, J.C. Vidal, F. Díaz-Hermida, A. Bugarín, A fuzzy syllogistic reasoning schema for generalized quantifiers, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 234 (2014) 79–96.
- [12] D.G. Schwartz, Dynamic reasoning with qualified syllogisms, *Artif. Intell.* 93 (1997) 103–167.
- [13] L.A. Zadeh, Syllogistic reasoning in fuzzy logic and its applications to usability and reasoning with dispositions, *IEEE Trans. Syst. Man Cybern.* 15 (1985) 754–765.
- [14] P. Murinová, Generalized intermediate syllogisms with more premises, in: *Proc. FUZZ-IEEE 2019, New Orleans, USA, 2019*.
- [15] V. Fiala, K. Červeňová, P. Murinová, On modelling of generalized Peterson's syllogisms with more premises, *Atlantis Stud. Uncertain. Model.* (2021) 375–382, 2021-09-19 Bratislava (2021).
- [16] V. Novák, P. Murinová, A formal model of the intermediate quantifiers “a few”, “several” and “a little”, in: *Proc. IFSA-NAFIPS 2019, Lafayette, USA, 2019*.
- [17] P. Murinová, V. Novák, Generalized Peterson's syllogisms with the quantifier “at least several (a few; a little)”, in: *Joint Proceedings of the 19th World Congress of the International Fuzzy Systems Association (IFSA), the 12th Conference of the European Society for Fuzzy Logic and Technology (EUSFLAT), and the 11th International Summer School on Aggregation Operators (AGOP), 2021*, pp. 367–374.
- [18] P. Andrews, *An Introduction to Mathematical Logic and Type Theory: To Truth Through Proof*, Kluwer, Dordrecht, 2002.
- [19] P. Murinová, V. Novák, The theory of intermediate quantifiers in fuzzy natural logic revisited and the model of “many”, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 388 (2020) 56–89.
- [20] V. Novák, A comprehensive theory of trichotomous evaluative linguistic expressions, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 159 (22) (2008) 2939–2969.
- [21] V. Novák, I. Perfilieva, A. Dvořák, *Insight into Fuzzy Modeling*, Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, New Jersey, 2016.
- [22] V. Novák, P. Murinová, A formal model of the intermediate quantifiers “A, Several, A little”, in: R. Kearfott, I. Batyrshin, M. Reformat, M. Ceberio, V. Kreinovich (Eds.), *Fuzzy Techniques: Theory and Applications*, Springer, Cham, Switzerland, 2019, pp. 429–441.
- [23] P. Peterson, *Intermediate Quantifiers. Logic, Linguistics, and Aristotelian Semantics*, Ashgate, Aldershot, 2000.

- [24] V. Novák, On fuzzy type theory, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 149 (2005) 235–273.
- [25] V. Novák, P. Murinová, P. Ferbas, Formal analysis of Peterson's rules for checking validity of syllogisms with intermediate quantifiers, *Int. J. Approx. Reason.* 150 (2022) 122–138.
- [26] P. Murinová, Graded structures of opposition in fuzzy natural logic, *Log. Univers.* 265 (2020) 495–522.